

Defining protocol and ontologies of the recipe visualisation tool

Marta Maria Vilardo, Andrea Borghini. 28 June 2026. Version No. 1.0

D4.3 Overview

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Abbreviations and acronyms

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.3 (D4.3): “Defining protocol and ontologies of the recipe visualisation tool” was produced by WP4: PREPPING – Wrangling & Curation of Data coordinated by the University of Milan (UMIL), with collaboration by WP3: INGREDIENTS – Data Collection.

D4.3 provides a report on the study of protocol and ontology for RELISH recipe visualisation tool, under the responsibility of UMIL with contributions from UNISG, UCC, UDUR, FA, BSC, and IST.

The present report describes the necessary tools and knowledge required to produce an ontology and variables for a prototype to visualise a recipe through storytelling. Particular emphasis is put on a recipe’s geographical and historical dimensions with respect to the mobility of people, ingredients, and knowledge.

D4.3 will also contribute to further work to be developed in WP3, WP5 and WP7 and WP8 (for Milestone 4.2).

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

The aim of **Deliverable 4.3 (D4.3)** is to review existing food ontologies and to discuss how they can help RELISH reframe European gastronomy: by treating recipes as digital objects, as cultural heritage, and as tools for imagining more sustainable and inclusive food futures. To do this, we need a clear and shared way to describe ingredients, dishes, processes, and eating practices so that different datasets, partners, and software components can all understand each other. **Food ontologies** provide this common language.

This report explains why food ontologies are important in the context of RELISH. This project treats recipes as part of Europe's cultural heritage and aims to understand how recipes shape food culture, education, and people's everyday lives. D4.3 is intended to clarify how we have assembled and integrated the material that underpins our ongoing work. In particular, it explains how we brought together insights from the relevant literature in the philosophy of food and in applied and formal ontology with the ideas, discussions, and materials that emerged from workshops and meetings with other members of our academic community. The aim is to outline the stages, process and results of a clear account of what has been achieved collectively over the past year.

1.1 Rationale

Across seven work packages, RELISH will create several digital and cultural tools, such as a web platform, a culinary map of Europe, future scenarios for food culture, and recipe visualisation tools. To make these tools work together, partners need a clear and shared way to describe ingredients, dishes, processes, places, and eating practices. Food ontologies provide this shared language.

A food ontology is a structured, machine-readable vocabulary that says what kinds of food-related phenomena exist (*e.g.*, ingredients, products, dishes, processes, and

qualities) and how they are connected. Using food ontologies, computers can organise and link information about recipes from many sources. In the context of RELISH, food ontologies:

- Make possible to describe recipes and food practices in a consistent way across countries and partners
- Support powerful but simple searches (*e.g.*, finding recipes without certain allergens, or recipes that use specific techniques like fermentation)
- Allow to link recipes to wider issues such as nutrition, sustainability, and food safety
- Provide a solid technical base for building the RELISH recipe visualisation tools and services

The overall objectives of WP4 are to:

1. Establish the theoretical and practical framework from which RELISH operates when dealing with existing research and information related to culinary cultural heritage
2. Support the UCD approach of the technical partners in the consortium from a cultural heritage perspective by identifying key questions and cultural assumptions that are relevant for RELISH
3. Assist partners in the development of key terms for analysis in culinary cultural activities organised on behalf of RELISH.
4. Identify and engage in conversation with institutional stakeholders in promoting culinary cultural heritage in local, national and at EU level

1.2 Description of the document

This report aims to provide a non-technical account of the work carried out on ontology development. It will present the state of the art, review related ontologies, and summarise the contributions already produced. The report will also identify current needs, outline how existing tools can address them, and assess which of these tools are currently usable for the development of a digital application.

The general objectives of D4.3 are to:

- Define a shared ontology and set of variables that enable representing recipes as cultural artefacts embedded in mobility, interdisciplinarity, and agency

- Design the protocols for visualisation, focussing on storytelling as a methodological lens; this includes tracking the movements of ingredients, people, and knowledge across time and space
- Prepare the conceptual and structural basis for the prototype of the recipe visualisation tool, which will be implemented and tested in WP4 and WP8

For this purpose, the **FoodOn vocabulary** (Dooley et al. 2018; see also Section 5.3 of this report)¹ is a useful model.

The document will also provide information on relevant conferences and events.

The report is conceived as a shared resource that can be circulated among stakeholders. It should contain the most relevant details, indicate the appropriate contact persons, and illustrate how the ontology can be applied in practice, supported by concrete examples.

D4.3 is a linchpin deliverable within RELISH:

- It bridges cultural theory (WP3) and technical implementation (WP8)
- It operationalises data collected in WP2 and prepares it for applied testing in WP5
- It provides conceptual coherence that underpins scenario-building in WP9

By embedding recipes within an ontology that highlights mobility, interdisciplinarity, and agency, D4.3 ensures that the RELISH project produces technical outputs and advances a cultural and historical understanding of recipes as dynamic, integrative, and sustainable elements of European culinary heritage.

1.3 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

D4.3 is a foundational step to developing the recipe visualisation tool. In the overall structure of RELISH, WP3 (“INGREDIENTS – Data Collection”) provides the data-collection groundwork, while WP4 (“PREPPING – Wrangling & Curation of Data”) develops the theoretical, analytical and data-curation framework.

D4.3 belongs to WP4 but depends on results from WP3. It defines the protocols and ontologies necessary to structure, interpret, and display recipes in ways that highlight their historical, geographical, and cultural dimensions.

¹ FoodOn: A farm to fork ontology website: <https://foodon.org/>

This work is situated in WP4: PREPPING – Wrangling & Curation of Data but its foundations and impacts are deeply interlinked with other WPs to ensure coherence for the overall RELISH project.

This deliverable is linked to the other RELISH WPs, specifically:

- **WP3 – INGREDIENTS:** Task 4.3 (T4.3), UMIL—with contributions from UNISG, UCC, UDUR, FA, BSC, and IST—develops the protocol and ontologies of the recipe visualisation tool. This ensures that data collected and curated by WP3 is semantically coherent, interoperable, and suitable for technical integration into the RELISH platform. Milestone 4.2 (M4.2) corresponds to this ontology being shared, agreed, and deployed by WP4 and WP8 by Month 18 (June 2026).
- **WP5 – COOKING:** Structured through D4.3, the recipe ontology informs WP5 trials and workshops. Pilots involving food professionals and wider publics will validate whether the protocols and visualisation methods are usable and meaningful in practice.
- **WP8 – COOLING DOWN:** The ontologies defined in Deliverable 4.3 are essential inputs for WP8, the technical backbone of the RELISH platform iteration. D4.3 guides WP8’s implementation of the RELISH platform’s data architecture and enables cross-use case interoperability. Without D4.3, the recipe visualisation tool could not be integrated into the larger technical framework.
- **WP9 – PLATING:** WP9 builds on the insights and visualisations emerging from WP4 and WP8 to develop speculative and future scenarios about the role of recipes in future European cultural heritage. D4.3 ensures that the data and conceptual structures underpinning these scenarios are robust and culturally grounded.

2 Food Ontologies Overview

Food ontology is a branch of applied ontology concerned with the structured representation of food-related entities, processes, and relations in a machine-readable form. In practical terms, a food ontology provides a controlled vocabulary and a conceptual framework that allows researchers, databases, and digital tools to refer to ingredients, dishes, preparation steps, qualities, and contexts in a consistent way.

In the context of RELISH, a food ontology matters because recipes are not only culinary instructions but also cultural, historical, and social artefacts that must be described in ways that are intelligible both to human users and to computational systems.

2.1 Applied ontology

Applied ontology provides the broader methodological framework within which food ontologies should be understood. In its philosophical background, ontology asks what kinds of entities exist in a given domain and how they are related. In knowledge representation, these questions are translated into constructing explicit and systematic models that support communication, comparison, data integration, and reasoning.

An ontology is therefore a **formal and shared conceptualisation of a domain**: it specifies relevant categories, relations and constraints, and makes explicit the assumptions that often remain implicit in ordinary language or in specialised practices. This definition is especially important in the food domain. Food-related phenomena cut across material, biological, cultural, spatial, economic and normative dimensions. The same item may be described, depending on context, as a biological product, an ingredient, a dish, a commodity, a cultural marker, a contaminant, and/or as waste.

Applied ontology helps to clarify many different levels of description without reducing them to a single perspective. It provides a way to distinguish merely terminological differences from deeper differences in classification, use, and interpretation.

2.2 Relevant applications

For RELISH, food ontologies are **technical tools** for standardising data, as well as **conceptual instruments** for modelling recipes as culturally and historically situated objects. They help identify which entities and relations must be represented if recipes are to be visualised, compared, and queried across different sources, communities, and digital applications.

Food ontologies are used to support interoperability across datasets and platforms, to improve search and retrieval, and to enable richer forms of analysis. They make it possible, for example, to connect recipes to ingredients, allergens, preparation techniques, geographical provenance, nutritional aspects, and historical variants.

In projects such as RELISH, recipes can be queried as text and as a structured object linked to broader cultural and technical dimensions. Ontologies are therefore useful because they provide the common semantic layer needed to integrate heterogeneous materials coming from archives, workshops, historical corpora, user studies, and digital platforms.

2.3 Background

Food ontologies developed from a broader history of knowledge organisation in information science, biomedical ontology, and semantic web technologies. More specifically, recent years have seen resource consolidation, such as **FoodOn** and **PO2/TransformON** (Weber et al. 2023), which demonstrate how ingredients, products, and food transformation processes can be represented in formal and reusable ways. Food ontology development has been driven by both theoretical interests and practical needs in areas such as food traceability, public health, nutrition, sustainability, and digital infrastructure design.

RELISH builds on this already existing landscape but extends it in a direction that is particularly attentive to recipes as objects of cultural heritage and historical interpretation.

The fields involved in developing food ontologies are interdisciplinary. They include applied ontology, philosophy of food, information science, food studies, digital humanities, human-computer interaction (HCI), and AI-oriented knowledge representation. This interdisciplinarity is particularly important for RELISH, because the project requires not technically robust and conceptually adequate models.

2.4 Philosophical approaches

In particular, **philosophical perspectives** are significant because they clarify what kind of entities recipes are, how identity and variation should be understood, what counts as authenticity, and how social and normative dimensions should be represented. Without this conceptual clarification, the formal model risks being technically efficient but culturally shallow.

A useful example is provided by a semantic representation of a recipe in which ingredients, processes, tools, temporal phases, and outputs are linked in a **knowledge graph**.² Such a model can represent a recipe not only as a sequence of instructions,

² An example knowledge graph from FoodOn (Dooley et al. 2018, 5) can be found here: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6550238/figure/Fig3/>

but also as a historically situated object connected to regional practices, ingredient mobility, sensory expectations, and possible variations. In this way, an ontology can support data management while enabling storytelling, visualisation, and comparison across traditions and time periods, all of which are central goals for RELISH.

Further, ontology has renewed significance for Artificial Intelligence, or Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Large Language Models (LLMs). Contemporary AI systems, especially those used for retrieval, recommendation, classification, and generative tasks, benefit from structured semantic resources that make concepts more explicit, link datasets more reliably, and improve interpretability. Ontology can support RELISH AI-related applications by making the relevant cultural dimensions and interpretations of recipes computationally tractable. This is particularly important when dealing with historical materials, multilingual corpora, and culturally sensitive distinctions that should not be flattened into purely statistical or numerical associations.

Philosophical approaches' broader significance is in showing that representations of recipes are never neutral: they always involve decisions about identity, authority, normativity, and relevance. Philosophy helps articulate these decisions explicitly and critically, while ontology engineering translates them into usable structures for digital systems. The contribution of RELISH is therefore to show how existing food ontologies can be enriched by integrating cultural, historical, and philosophical reflection and thus support more meaningful digital tools for European culinary heritage.

2.5 Ontology as layered ecosystem

Food ontologies can be understood as a **layered ecosystem of semantic resources**. Not all ontologies and controlled vocabularies operate at the same level of abstraction or serve the same function. Some provide very general categories, while others are designed for specific domains, applications, or regulatory tasks. Clarifying these levels is important for RELISH, because the recipe visualisation tool will need to combine conceptual, cultural, and technical resources without treating them as interchangeable.

At the most **abstract level**, top-level or foundational ontologies provide general categories such as object, process, quality, role, function and agent. Examples include Basic Formal Ontology (BFO), Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering (DOLCE), Unified Foundational Ontology (UFO) / gentle Unified Foundational Ontology (gUFO), Process Specification Language (PSL), and Business Objects Reference Ontology (BORO). These frameworks do not focus specifically on food, but they offer a conceptual backbone for representing entities, processes,

qualities, social objects, and temporal change. They are helpful for when RELISH decides, for example, whether recipes should be modelled primarily as information artefacts, social objects, normative plans, workflows, or process descriptions.

A **second level** is occupied by mid-level ontologies, which refine foundational categories for broad interconnected domains. The Environment Ontology (ENVO), for instance, represents environments, places and anthropogenic contexts. Such resources are important because recipes and food practices are embedded in landscapes, infrastructures, agricultural systems, spaces of preparation, places of consumption and cultural settings.

A **third level** includes domain ontologies specifically concerned with food, nutrition, behaviour, sustainability or transformation processes. FoodOn is the central reference here, since it provides a structured representation of food materials, food products and farm-to-fork processes. PO2/TransformON³ is also especially relevant for RELISH because it focuses on food, feed, bioproducts, biowaste and transformation processes. Other resources—such as Ontology for Nutritional Studies (ONS), Behaviour Change Intervention Ontology (BCIO), Community on Food Consumer Science (COMFOCUS) Ontology or the Sustainability Core Ontology (SCO)—can contribute to more specific modelling needs related to nutrition, behaviour, consumer practices, and sustainability.

A **fourth level** is represented by application ontologies, taxonomies and controlled vocabularies designed for narrower tasks. Food Allergen Traceability Ontology (FATO), for example, focuses on allergen traceability; FoodEx2 supports food safety and exposure assessment; Langua aLimentaria (LanguaL) provides a legacy classification system for food composition; the Food and Agriculture Organisation's (FAO) AGROVOC offers a multilingual controlled vocabulary for agriculture and food. These resources are not all ontologies in the strict sense, but they can support interoperability, annotation, search, and regulatory alignment.

Finally, **conceptual frameworks** such as *gastrospace*s (Bonotti et al. 2025) and *foodscapes* models (see for example Fodor and Jalas 2026; Jung et al. 2022; Foodscapes, n.d.) represent socio-spatial and cultural dimensions of food. They are usually less formalised than computational ontologies, but they help identify crucial categories for RELISH: places of production and consumption, norms of access, forms of commensality, cultural meaning, social interaction and situated food practices.

The practical implication is that no single ontology can cover all relevant dimensions of recipes. FoodOn can provide a core semantic reference for ingredients and food products; PO2/TransformON can support modelling transformations and processes;

³ PO2/TransformON is based on the Process and Observation Ontology (PO2).

application vocabularies can address allergens, traceability and regulatory concerns; conceptual frameworks can help represent cultural, spatial and narrative dimensions.

The task is to build an **interoperable semantic layer** in which different resources are reused, aligned, and extended according to the needs of the recipe visualisation tool.

3 Process

This section concretises the general objectives of D4.3 (see **Section 1.2**). It explains how these objectives were followed: which materials were drawn on, how these materials were assembled, and how they were analysed. Overall, this section makes explicit the design, sources, and interpretive procedures used to reach a final protocol.

Concretely, D4.3 aims to:

- Provide a conceptual and theoretical framework for thinking about recipes as cultural and informational objects
- Connect this framework with existing food-related ontologies (such as FoodOn and PO2/TransformON)
- Identify the minimum requirements for a recipe visualisation tool that can be used across RELISH
- Support other WPs by offering a shared vocabulary and a set of reference concepts for recipes, food practices, and their cultural and historical dimensions

To achieve these aims, the research assembles and interprets heterogeneous materials from internal meetings and workshops within RELISH, specialised events and hackathons, and academic literature reviewed. These materials were read, discussed, compared, and synthesised into the conceptual and technical results presented in the following sections.

3.1 Meetings, workshops, and hackathons

D4.3 is first shaped by the practical needs and questions emerging from the RELISH consortium. Throughout WP3 and WP4, partners met regularly in both online and in-person formats. These meetings involved:

- Recurring online coordination meetings involving all members: 2-hour weekly meeting between WP leads and the lead author, and a weekly meeting on recipes with other members of the consortium
- Thematic discussions focussed on recipe identity, cultural heritage, temporal aspects of food processes, and the technical constraints of the future RELISH platform
- Joint sessions between cultural and technical partners, in which conceptual questions (e.g., “What is a recipe?” or “What counts as the ‘same’ recipe across cultures and time?”) were explicitly related to data modelling questions

Minutes, slides, and informal notes from these meetings functioned as primary documentary sources. These sources helped to identify:

- Which aspects of recipes mattered most for different partners (e.g., identity, authorship, authenticity, locality, temporality, sensory properties)
- Which ontologies and standards were already in use or considered promising (e.g., FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI), Phenotype and Trait Ontology (PATO), COMFOCUS, and others)
- Which user stories and use cases the recipe visualisation tool would need to support (e.g., exploring local variants, tracing ingredient mobility, highlighting allergens, representing temporal phases of preparation and consumption)

In parallel, the report builds on material generated during workshops, conferences, and hackathons closely related to RELISH’s themes. These include, among others:

- A preparatory workshop, “Foundations for Food and Food Systems Ontologies: Mapping Representational Variants,” held at the Department of Philosophy of the University of Milan (2024), which provided an interdisciplinary forum on how to represent food, recipes, and food systems in formal ontologies
- The Integrated Food Ontology Workshops (IFOW 2019–2025), which brought together ontology engineers, food scientists, and philosophers to discuss foundational and applied issues in food-related ontologies (specifically IFOW 2025, in the 15th international conference on formal ontology in information system (FOIS) organised in Catania, 8-12th September)
- The Graduate Workshop on Food and Philosophy, in Milan, 25-26th March 2025

- The McGill Centre for the Convergence of Health and Economics (MCCHE) Convergent Innovation Webinar Series at McGill University, in which digital food transformation, traceability, and the role of recipes in “bots in the kitchen” and AI-mediated food systems were discussed
- The Hackathon Firenze (May 2025), organised by Marta Vilaro and Andrea Borghini (UMIL), Damion Dooley (Simon Fraser University) and Salvatore Florio (University of Oslo), which focussed on representing temporality in recipes and food processes and on how top-level ontologies and FoodOn can capture phases, efficiency, and contextual aspects of food practices
- Culinary Mind seminars in Milan on philosophy of food, organised by Marta Vilaro (UMIL), Andrea Borghini (UMIL), Nicola Piras (University of Minho), Michelangelo Bestazzi (University of Minho), Sara Madera Gomez (UMIL) and Elena Bossini (University of Sassari), on 26th November, 2nd December and 15th December 2025, with more planned for 2026
- Discussion group on philosophy of food, both online and in person

The lead author of the report also attended two summer schools: the C-FORS in Foundational Ontology in Oslo from 20th to 23rd May, 2025 and the Interdisciplinary School on Applied Ontology in Catania from 15th to 19th September 2025.

In particular, the Hackathon Firenze provided rich material. Discussions revolved around three families of challenges:

1. **Phases:** How to represent constitutive and non-constitutive phases in recipes (*e.g.*, leavening and baking for Neapolitan pizza, or extraction time for espresso), and how temporal constraints (such as maximum duration) contribute to the identity of a food product.
2. **Efficiency:** How to conceptualise accelerated or extended processes (*e.g.*, chemically aged rum, iceberg lettuce with extended shelf life, UHT milk) and how to compare “standard” and “efficient” processes within an ontological framework.
3. **Context:** How to model seasonality, typicality, and the transition from niche to global foods (*e.g.*, octopus in Catalonia, spaghetti al pomodoro, quinoa, sushi), including the roles of locality, authority, appropriateness, and induced seasonality.

Further contributions at the Hackathon examined how different top-level ontologies (such as BFO/COB,⁴ CCO/BORO,⁵ UFO, and DOLCE) handle temporal entities and processes, and how these choices affect the representation of recipes as occurrents, social objects, or abstract entities. Additional sessions considered the current and potential treatment of temporal aspects in FoodOn, such as process durations, temporal regions (*e.g.*, “Thanksgiving”), reversible and irreversible processes, and labelling time conditions in process diagrams. These discussions offered concrete test cases and highlighted open modelling questions that RELISH must address when designing tools for recipe visualisation.

Program, abstracts, presentation slides, and notes from these events were treated as contextual evidence. They helped to locate RELISH within a wider, already active research community and identify convergences (*e.g.*, the central role of FoodOn and PO2/TransformON) and open gaps, especially around cultural heritage, temporal representation, recipe identity, and narrative visualisation.

This protocol development thus relies on continuous, iterative dialogue between RELISH partners and external communities working on food ontologies, philosophy of food, and the temporality of food processes.

3.2 Corpus: Literature and project documents

Alongside meetings, workshops and hackathons, a central component involved constructing a literature and sources corpus, which is documented in the **References** section of this deliverable. The corpus is interdisciplinary and includes:

- **Philosophy of food and recipes:** literature that discuss recipes as social and cultural objects, metaphysical accounts of food and dishes, authenticity, authorship, norms, tacit knowledge, and sensorial identity. Authors in this group explore, for example, whether recipes should be understood as texts, norms, plans, or cultural artefacts, and how these choices affect questions of identity and variation.
- **Food ontologies and semantic technologies:** Foundational papers and technical reports on FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, COMFOCUS and related ontological frameworks, including work on OBI, PATO, and integrating food-relevant resources within the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) Foundry. These contributions clarify how ingredients, processes,

⁴ BFO/COB anchors the Core Ontology for Biology and Biomedicine (COB) in Basic Formal Ontology (BFO).

⁵ CCO/BORO combines Common Core Ontologies (CCO) with the Business Objects Reference Ontology (BORO).

nutritional properties, and food system entities can be represented in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) and linked across datasets.

- **Consumer behaviour, nutrition, and digital health:** Studies on ontology-based modelling of consumer food behaviour, AI-supported nutrition and personalisation, and digital infrastructures for food data. These studies illustrate how semantic technologies are used in practice and suggest potential uses and constraints for RELISH.
- **Conceptual and methodological ontology work:** Research on ontology governance, evidence and conclusion ontologies, and the role of AI in maintaining and extending formal ontologies. This literature informs how RELISH might manage the evolution of its own semantic resources.
- **General metaphysical and meta-ontological references:** Literature addressing how categories are chosen and justified, and how social and normative objects (*e.g.*, recipes, dishes, and food-related events) should be treated in ontology.

Rather than aiming at an exhaustive coverage of all existing writings on food and ontology, the authors adopted a purposeful sampling strategy, selecting sources according to their relevance for RELISH's goals and based on criteria such as their:

- Being widely recognition as a reference point in the philosophy of food and recipes
- Being a central resource in the development or application of food-related ontologies
- Explicitly addressing issues of authenticity, authorship, recipe identity, temporality, and cultural heritage
- Illustrating how ontologies can be used in practical domains such as nutrition, consumer behaviour, and traceability

In addition to published academic work, the corpus includes project-generated documents:

- Internal reports, concept notes, and sketches circulated among RELISH partners
- Minutes and slide decks from internal meetings, workshops, and the Hackathon Firenze
- Abstracts and presentation materials from related conferences and webinar series

The resulting corpus conceptually and empirically grounds the development of a RELISH protocol for defining ontologies. Every major claim about recipes, ontology, temporality, and visualisation in later sections can be traced back to one or more items in this set of sources.

3.3 Interpretation and themes

Once the corpus was assembled, the authors conducted an interpretive literature review common to theory-building and mixed-methods contexts. The process can be summarised in three partially overlapping phases:

I. EXPLORATORY READING AND MAPPING

All items in the corpus—both publications and project documents—were read to identify sources' main questions, key concepts, and proposed distinctions (*e.g.*, “recipe as social object,” “normative plans,” “sensorial identity,” “authenticity,” “temporality and phases,” “efficiency,” “typicality and seasonality”).

During this phase, short memos were taken to record recurring themes and potential tensions (*e.g.*, between descriptive and normative views of recipes, between cultural heritage and globalisation, between technical aims of ontologies and philosophical pluralism).

II. THEMATIC CODING AND CLUSTERING

Recurring themes were turned into provisional analytical categories. Examples include:

- Identity and persistence of recipes over time and across variants
- Authorship, naming, and intellectual property
- Authenticity, territoriality, and legal protection
- Vagueness, tacit knowledge, and embodied skills
- Sensorial properties and aesthetic dimensions
- Temporal phases, duration, and efficiency of food processes
- Seasonality, typicality, and context of consumption

- Formal modelling of recipes (*e.g.*, plans, workflows, processes)
- Governance, traceability, and consumer behaviour

The literature and project documents were revisited with these categories in mind, and passages were associated with one or more themes—a process analogous to qualitative coding.

III. SYNTHESIS AND TRANSLATION INTO PROJECT-ORIENTED LANGUAGE

The coded materials were synthesised into narrative summaries that could directly inform the structure of the report and the design choices for RELISH.

Philosophical discussions were translated into terminology accessible for non-philosophical audiences in RELISH, without losing conceptual precision.

Technical work on ontologies was interpreted in light of RELISH use cases, highlighting which tools and distinctions are immediately relevant for the recipe visualisation tool, and which ones remain more contextual or experimental.

This strategy differs from a purely systematic review in the narrow sense (with predefined search strings and quantitative indicators). It privileges conceptual depth and cross-disciplinary integration over exhaustive enumeration, appropriate to constructing a shared and RELISH-applicable conceptual and ontological framework.

3.4 Analytical strategy

WP4's analytical strategy was to **triangulate** types of sources from scholarly literature, technical ontology materials, internal meetings or external gatherings feedback.

Issues that emerged in internal meetings (*e.g.*, difficulties in aligning cultural heritage with technical constraints, or questions about how to represent temporal phases of recipes) were checked against the academic literature to see how similar problems had been formulated and addressed elsewhere.

Concepts developed in the philosophy of food—such as “recipes as normative plans,” “sensorial identity,” or “typicality”—were tested from the point of view of ontology engineers and data curators during workshops, IFOW sessions, and the Hackathon Firenze, where concrete modelling examples were explored.

Technical requirements expressed by RELISH’s platform developers (e.g., the need to model processes, ingredients, allergens, temporal durations, and consumer behaviours) were examined in relation to existing ontologies and to theoretical work on meta-ontology and social objects.

Figure 1: Triangulation strategy for corpus of sources and materials.

Triangulation avoids two symmetrical risks:

1. Purely **internal** reasoning, in which the project invents its own categories without reference to established scholarship.
2. Purely **external** importation, in which existing theories and ontologies are simply taken off the shelf without adjusting them to RELISH’s specific objectives and constraints.

This strategy creates dialogue between internal project needs and external bodies of knowledge. In concrete terms:

- The objectives formulated in this section reflect both philosophical debates and the practical needs and concerns voiced in RELISH discussions.

- The methodological reflections in Section 4 draw on ontology engineering literature but are reshaped to fit both the “recipe as cultural heritage” perspective and the temporal challenges highlighted at the Hackathon Firenze.
- Section 5 documents the events and discussions that provided empirical grounding and case-based intuition, including experimental modelling exercises and temporal case studies.
- Section 6 distils what RELISH can concretely reuse from existing ontologies and where it needs to extend or adapt them, especially in relation to temporal representation and context.

The analytical strategy is also iterative: preliminary formulations of concepts and requirements were brought back to the consortium, discussed, revised, tested in events such as IFOW and the Hackathon Firenze, and then refined through further reading and comparison with external work.

3.5 Review results

The process described above—assembling meetings, workshops, hackathons, literature, and internal documents, and analysing them through interpretive, thematic, and triangulated procedures—leads to a series of specific results, which are detailed in the following sections.

Among these results are:

1. **A refined understanding of recipes as hybrid cultural–informational objects**, integrating insights from philosophy, ontology engineering, and practical food studies:

Clarified definitions for recipes as normative plans, cultural artefacts, and process specifications.

Clarified roles for identity or “sameness,” variation, authenticity, and authorship.

2. **A set of key dimensions** for recipe identity, variation, temporality and context:

Key Dimensions: Ingredients, procedures, sensorial goals, authorship, tradition, territorial and legal constraints, temporal phases, efficiency, seasonality, typicality.

3. **Recommendations for uses and limitations** regarding FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and related ontologies within RELISH:

Uses: Existing ontologies provide abstract standards and concrete tools that can support recipe visualisation, semantic search, traceability, and scenario-building.

Limitations: Temporal modelling in FoodOn can be expanded and/or refined (as identified during Hackathon Firenze).

4. **A minimal architecture** for the recipe visualisation tool:

Basic architecture: A data layer, semantic layer, backend, and user-facing frontend organised around the conceptual distinctions and ontological choices developed in here

Included/novel features: Temporal phases, heritage aspects, and typicality.

5. **A set of competency questions** that connect the theoretical analysis to evaluable system behaviour.

“Which recipes in a given region use fermentation?”

“Which variants of a traditional recipe avoid specific allergens?”

“How have ingredients or processes for a dish changed over time across different localities?”

“Which recipes are typically associated with a given season or event?”

Each of these results can be read as a synthesis of multiple strands of evidence: internal discussions, workshop and hackathon insights, and scholarly literature. The report therefore does not present isolated opinions, but a reasoned consolidation of perspectives coming from different disciplines and institutional contexts.

The chosen approach is appropriate for a deliverable whose main role is to act as a keystone conceptual and ontological resource for RELISH. By explicitly describing its origins in assembled materials—meetings, workshops, hackathons, and a carefully selected literature corpus—and by making its interpretive procedures transparent, the report provides a solid, accountable foundation for the technical and cultural work that will follow in other Work Packages.

These results are further detailed and justified in the following sections.

4 Developing Applied Ontologies

The aim of this section is to prepare the ground for **applied ontologies**. We look at recipes and related food concepts (such as identity, authorship, authenticity, locality, and sensory properties) to clarify **what they are** and **how they work**. Spelling out these conceptual discussions will ease their translation into formal vocabularies and data models used in digital systems (including applied ontologies such as FoodOn and PO2/TransformON).

In short, this section provides the conceptual toolkit that will later allow us to represent recipes and food practices in a precise, machine-readable, and practical manner.

4.1 The study of recipes

The study of recipes has recently become an important subject for people working in philosophy, food studies, and digital knowledge systems. Philosophers examine what recipes are and what role they play in people's lives. Experts in "formal ontology" (the design of structured vocabularies for computers) create tools like FoodOn and PO2/TransformON that help different digital systems talk to each other about food in a precise way (Dooley et al. 2018).

Philosophical perspectives demonstrate limitations to characterising recipes as simple or technical lists of instructions. Instead, they consider recipes as complex cultural and informational objects involving identity, authorship, tradition, and norms about what counts as "right" or "wrong" (Borghini 2015; Borghini and Piras 2020). This way of conceiving recipes fields basic questions about what recipes are, how we know things through them, and what social role(s) they play.

Literature on food ontology borrows from philosophy (which clarifies ideas like "recipe", "local food", "food values") and formal ontology (such as FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and traceability frameworks). Drawing these fields together yields a shared foundation for digital tools that has structural, conceptual, and semantic dimensions.

From this point of view, a recipe is a structure comprising several semantically identified categories and elements, including:

- Ingredients and their quantities
- Procedures and transformations (what to do and in what order)

- Tools and conditions (time, temperature, place)
- Cultural and normative aspects (tradition, locality, acceptable variations)

From this structure, philosophy of food then considers conceptual implications and questions regarding, for example:

- The identity of recipes (when is a recipe “the same”?)
- The relationship between food and territory
- Ethical and normative aspects of food production
- How digital technologies affect cooking and culinary practices

From here, WP4 grounds and applies the structure and concept into a guideline for RELISH (see **Figure 2**), summarising the questions, methods, outcomes, and functions that an ontology of recipes could help embed within a visualisation tool.

Figure 2: Summative guide to D4.3 questions, methods, outcomes, and functions for an ontology of recipes.

4.2 Key questions

WHAT KIND OF THING IS A RECIPE?

One of the main debates concerns the basic question: *What kind of thing is a recipe?*
Different answers have been proposed:

- One approach treats recipes as **social objects**, similar to norms, rules, or laws. In this view, a recipe exists because a community recognises, uses, and passes it on, not because of any particular written or digital copy (Borghini 2015; Sciacca 2020).
- A second approach treats recipes as **information artefacts**. In this sense, recipes are items that carry information, appearing in cookbooks, websites, videos, or oral traditions, and their main function is to transmit cooking knowledge (Dooley, Weber, et al. 2024).
- A third approach sees recipes as **plans** or **algorithms**: structured sequences of steps that guide the cook from raw ingredients to the finished dish.

Recent philosophical work tends to integrate these views (Borghini and Piras 2020; Serpico et al. 2020). Following Borghini (2015) and Borghini and Engisch (2022), recipes are best understood as cultural artefacts that carry information and have a normative, action-guiding role:

- They are **cultural artefacts** because they are created, transmitted, and modified within communities.
- They are **information-bearing** because they are meant to encode and transmit cooking know-how.
- They are **normative** because they do not simply describe what happens in a kitchen— they tell us what to do in order to obtain a certain result.

This view places recipes closer to **plans** than to descriptions. Recipes give us directives (“*Do this, then that*”) in a specific order to achieve a specific dish.

However, unlike abstract rules, recipes aim at concrete, sensory outcomes: success depends on whether the dish actually tastes, feels, and looks as expected. While the algorithm analogy is still useful, unlike rigid computer algorithms, recipes often require adaptation to context and rely on embodied knowledge and experience.

Seeing recipes as normative, information-bearing cultural artefacts helps explain:

- How a recipe can remain “the same” across different formats (oral, written, digital), while still prescribing specific actions, and
- How this understanding supports debates about authorship, authenticity, and digital circulation, wherein recipes are both cultural heritage and practical instructions.

In this way, recipes are **hybrid entities** that connect social ontology (how social objects exist), philosophy of information, and philosophy of action.

WHAT MAKES TWO RECIPES “THE SAME”?

Another central issue is the identity of a recipe: under what conditions can we say that two recipes are “the same recipe”?

Different possible criteria have been proposed, for example:

- The presence of core ingredients
- The proportions among those ingredients
- The techniques or processes used
- The intended sensory profile (taste, texture, appearance)
- The historical or social lineage (how the recipe has been named and passed down)

In formal modelling terms, “sameness” can be treated at different levels. Perfect identity would require no relevant difference between two recipe representations. In most practical cases, however, recipe identity depends on “close enough” similarity across selected dimensions. These dimensions may include ingredient similarity, proportional similarity, process similarity, organoleptic similarity, functional similarity, cultural lineage, and permitted ranges of variation.

Recent work suggests that no single criterion is enough by itself. Hybrid models seem more convincing. For example, Serpico et al. (2020), studying cocktail recipes, argue that recipes have a “core” that must be preserved but allow for variation around that core. This explains how certain changes are accepted as variations, while others are seen as creating a new recipe.

Different classification systems set different thresholds for when a variation counts as a new recipe:

- In **authorship-sensitive** approaches (Borghini and Gandolini 2020), the authority of the creator matters. A chef or author may decide which modifications are still part of “their” recipe and which count as innovation.
- In **context-sensitive** approaches, identity depends more on social and historical context: what counts as “the same recipe” can depend on what a community recognises as continuous with its practices (Sciaccia 2020).

This brings us to the distinction between **essential** and **non-essential features**. Some substitutions (*e.g.*, olive oil vs. butter) may be seen as acceptable, while others change the recipe so much that they create something new.

Recent literature tends to reject the idea of a fixed universal essence for all recipes and instead supports more flexible frameworks, which WP3 is developing with **vital, complementary, and optional points** (see RELISH D3.4) in recipes, combining a necessary core with structured degrees of freedom. In so doing, we can make reasoned decisions about “same” and “different” across places, times, and sources (Serpico et al. 2020; Sciacca 2020).

HOW DO TRADITION AND AUTHORSHIP SHAPE RECIPES?

Recipes occupy a space between communal inheritance and individual authorship. On the one hand, recipes evolve through **communal use**: oral transmission, local adaptation, and repeated practice shape dishes that no single person can fully claim. Communities often fix certain rules for what counts as the “real thing” and reject other versions (*e.g.*, rejecting “carbonara with cream” as inauthentic). Thus, recipes are part of a shared normative framework.

On the other hand, recipes can be linked to specific authors. Borghini and Gandolini (2020) propose a taxonomy of culinary authorship. They distinguish, for example:

- The **originator**, who first invents a combination
- The **codifier**, who writes down and stabilises a version
- The **interpreter**, who offers variations
- The **branding author**, who turns a dish into a recognisable “signature” with a name and reputation

This view shows that authorship in cooking is rarely the work of a single isolated genius. It is layered and often shared among many actors.

Baldini (2020) adds that spontaneity and creativity are key when a dish becomes a chef’s “signature dish.” Even within a tradition, a chef can introduce new pairings, techniques, or presentations that mark the dish as distinctly theirs.

Names play an important role here. They communicate authenticity and authority:

- Some names carry territorial weight (*e.g.*, “Parmigiano Reggiano”, “Neapolitan pizza”), linking a recipe to a region and community and often protected by law

- Other names foreground personal authorship (e.g., “Massimo Bottura’s Five Ages of Parmigiano”), where a famous ingredient or dish is reinterpreted as a vehicle for an individual chef’s creativity

In both cases, naming helps to fix expectations, assign credit, and mark boundaries: who can use the name, and under what conditions.

Thus, recipes should not be seen as purely communal nor purely individual products. They are hybrid cultural objects shaped by both shared practice and individual creativity, and reinforced by naming practices that carry normative and territorial meaning.

THE QUESTION OF AUTHENTICITY

Authenticity is a key issue. It is not an objective property of recipes or dishes, but rather a **social and normative judgment**. As Sciacca (2020) notes, calling a dish “authentic” means appealing to tradition and community standards, not just to facts about ingredients or procedures. Authenticity works like a rule: it sets boundaries between acceptable and unacceptable variations. Its force comes from collective recognition and cultural memory.

However, such recognition is not homogeneous. Authenticity claims are often shaped by different forms of authority, including community endorsement, expert judgment, institutional recognition, and, in some cases, authorial or chef-based authority. What counts as “more authentic” may depend on who is making the claim, in what context, and for what purpose.

Claims to authenticity or frequently **claims to tradition** (continuity with past practices, “*the same recipe handed down through generations*”) and territory (connection to place and local methods). However, authenticity is rarely an all-or-nothing matter. In practice, there are often hierarchies of authenticity, as well as spaces of negotiation and flexibility. Some variants may be treated as fully authentic, others as acceptable but secondary, and others again as inauthentic. These distinctions may shift depending on whether the relevant authority is a local community, a chef, a heritage institution, a legal framework, or a wider public.

Legal tools such as Protected Designations of Origin (PDOs) and Protected Geographical Indications (PGIs) turn some of these cultural norms into formal rules. They protect recipes and products as cultural property, but also exclude practices judged to be inauthentic (Borghini and Engisch 2022). Yet, even legal and institutional forms of authenticity do not eliminate negotiation. Rather, they stabilise only some of the criteria that communities and experts continue to interpret in practice.

In the digital age, authenticity is also **performed online**. Through websites, blogs, and social media, producers and communities tell stories, share images, and use symbolic elements—like references to terroir, artisanal methods, or the “grandmother in the kitchen”—to claim authenticity. Digital media, in this way, transforms how people make claims to authenticity; they amplify, rank, negotiate, and reframe it.

HOW DO SENSORY PROPERTIES DEFINE A RECIPE?

Recipes can tell us what to do. They also specify, explicitly or implicitly, an organoleptic objective: they characterise the intended output material not only by its ingredients and procedures, but also by expected qualities such as taste, smell, texture, appearance, and mouthfeel.

For example:

- A risotto should be creamy but with rice still firm
- A soufflé should rise and have a delicate texture
- Tiramisù should balance creaminess, coffee bitterness, and cocoa aroma

If these expected **organoleptic** properties are missing, we may no longer recognise the dish as the same.

Bordini (2022) introduces the idea of **sensorial identity**: recipes are oriented toward producing a particular sensory experience. Listing ingredients and instructions is therefore not sufficient to fully characterise the intended output of a recipe, because many organoleptic qualities are subjective, gradual, and context dependent. This emphasises the embodied, lived nature of cooking.

Fox (2020) connects this to **aesthetics**. Sensory aspects—taste, texture, appearance—are not just practical standards; they have an aesthetic dimension. Recipes thus intersect everyday practice and art. They mediate between shared norms (“*This is what a proper risotto is like*”) and aesthetic values (harmony, surprise, expressiveness).

Further, distinguishing between dishes often depends on their sensory and aesthetic profile. Two recipes might look similar on paper but differ in the sensory experience they produce.

Taken together, these ideas suggest that recipes are hybrid artefacts whose identities depend on:

- Material composition and procedures

- Communal recognition
- The sensory and aesthetic outcomes at which they aim

This places recipes within both the ontology of cultural artefacts and food aesthetics.

WHY ARE RECIPES OFTEN VAGUE?

Many recipes contain vague expressions such as “season to taste,” “cook until golden”, or “add enough water.” This vagueness is part of **how recipes work**. They leave room for interpretation, which must be filled using the cook’s experience and skills.

Vague phrases like “enough salt” or “right elasticity” assume that the cook has practical knowledge: they know from experience how something should look, feel, or taste. This is a form of **tacit knowledge** (Polanyi 1966): know-how that cannot be fully captured in words and is expressed in action

Fox (2020) argues that this vagueness is essential. If one tried to remove it completely by over-specifying every detail, recipes would lose much of their flexibility. However, highly specified recipes remain very relevant in industrial contexts, where they often function as formulations: precise descriptions of ingredients, processes, and quality criteria designed to reproduce a stable product. Conditions such as ingredient quality, equipment, and personal taste vary too much to be fully standardised in ordinary cooking contexts.

Vagueness also supports **creativity** and **adaptation**. “Season to taste” explicitly invites the cook to adjust according to their preferences, cultural background, and local conditions. In this sense, vagueness is a normative feature: it defines a space where the cook’s judgment is required and legitimate.

Rather than making them unreliable, vagueness is part of what makes recipes workable, adaptable, and expressive. This point also connects with the project’s own work on “Food Memories,” (see RELISH D3.1) wherein facilitators approach cooking and food-related storytelling through learned techniques and skills, and where the workshop manual and its later expansion elicit practical, embodied, and not fully codified forms of knowledge for understanding culinary practices.

ARE RECIPES CULTURAL OBJECTS?

Recipes are cultural objects that change over time. They are transmitted from generation to generation and form lineages or “families” of variations. The familiar

phrase, “My grandmother’s recipe,” captures how recipes carry memory, identity, and emotion.

However, inherited recipes still frequently change due to:

- Ingredient substitutions
- New cooking technologies
- Evolving tastes and dietary habits

These changes create genealogies: groups of related recipes that trace back to a common ancestor but look different in practice.

The history of a recipe is shaped by a tension between continuity and rupture—some changes are accepted as legitimate adaptations that keep the recipe “the same,” while other changes are perceived as breaking with tradition altogether (*e.g.*, heated debates about cream in carbonara or pineapple on pizza).

Sciacca (2020) suggests that models sensitive to authorship help us understand these cultural dynamics. Avoiding the assumption that recipes are simply anonymous cultural products, Sciacca underlines how their cultural provenance is often tied to names, in the form of:

- Family attributions (“grandma’s lasagne”)
- Communal attributions (“Neapolitan pizza”)
- Individual creations (“Bottura’s Parmigiano dish”)

Attribution to an author can both preserve and transform identity. It keeps continuity alive (“*This is still grandma’s recipe*”) while allowing new branches to form when a cook radically reinterprets a dish.

From this angle, recipes have a diachronic ontology: they persist through time by balancing preservation and change. Stories about who created, adapted, or protected a recipe are part of what defines a recipe. At the same time, this diachronic persistence is fragile. In historical or archaeological contexts, parts of the relevant information may be lost, leaving only partial traces from which a recipe or food practice could be reconstructed. For this reason, the identity of a recipe should not be modelled only through explicit textual records, but also through provenance links, material evidence, oral transmission, and historically situated interpretations.

4.3 The meta-theoretical status of recipe identity

Debates about the identity of recipes include who gets to decide and by which criteria. In this sense, recipes are **meta-ontological**: they concern how people choose and justify their categories (Sider 2011; Thomasson 2015).

If the identity of a recipe is partly a matter of norms and decisions, then formal ontologies (such as FoodOn and related systems) must also:

- Represent who sets identity criteria (*e.g.*, legal bodies, chefs, communities)
- Record how these criteria can differ across contexts
- Allow for multiple overlapping “identity regimes” (*e.g.*, legal, culinary, or local community standards)

This means that ontologies should include meta-level information about the origin and authority of identity claims. Users should be able to query recipes under different perspectives (*e.g.*, “according to EU law” vs. “according to local tradition”).

In parallel with philosophical work, ontological engineering has created powerful semantic tools to support food traceability, nutrition research, and cultural heritage. These tools build on the idea that recipes:

- Are normative cultural artefacts with hybrid identities
- Are realised through tacit skills, improvisation, and communal evolution
- Raise meta-level questions about who defines identity criteria
- Require formal models that can represent both facts and norms

In this way, ontologies provide the digital infrastructure needed to bring philosophical insights about recipes into practical, interoperable tools.

These works illustrate how semantic technologies are being used in practice and suggest potential uses and constraints for RELISH. For example, FoodOn provides a strong model for the standardised representation of ingredients, products, allergens, and traceability-related categories; PO2/TransformON offers particularly useful tools for representing transformation processes and workflow-like steps in food production; and COMFOCUS shows how ontology-based modelling can be extended to consumer food behaviour and more sustainable eating practices.

Figure 3 sums up these results, suggesting key aspects that any recipe model should aim to cover.

Figure 3: A modelling approach to recipes as hybrid objects for RELISH.

5 Method: Formal Modelling

Recent years have seen growing interest in how to model recipes in a precise, machine-readable way, especially in ontology engineering and knowledge representation. In this context, ontology refers to a **structured vocabulary** that lets computers represent and connect concepts in a consistent way.

Recipes, as this report has detailed, are inadequately represented as technical instructions. They reflect culture, norms (“how things should be done”), and procedures. So, if RELISH models them, we need tools that can capture both information (ingredients, steps) and processes (what happens over time in the kitchen).

A useful analogy comes from the life sciences: experimental protocols can be represented as **workflows** with *inputs* (materials, tools, energy), *processes* (mixing, heating, measuring), and *outputs* (samples, results). Recipes can be treated similarly:

- **Inputs:** ingredients, tools, energy (*e.g.*, heat)
- **Processes:** cutting, boiling, frying, fermenting, mixing
- **Outputs:** intermediate preparations and final dishes

Once recipes are represented like this, they can be used by computers for tasks such as advanced search, automatic recipe adaptation, and integration into AI systems. Projects such as FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW) have contributed to this effort by asking: How can we represent recipes and food processes in ways that remain faithful to their cultural meaning, while also being easy for machines to process (Dooley, Weber, et al. 2024; Weber et al. 2023)?

5.1 How to formalise recipes

From the point of view of formal ontology (the structured vocabularies used in applied systems), recipes can be modeled as workflows:

1. **Inputs** – ingredients, water, energy, tools
2. **Process steps** – actions like cutting, boiling, frying, fermenting, mixing
3. **Outputs** – intermediate preparations (*e.g.*, dough, sauce) and final dishes
4. **Constraints** – required techniques, times, and temperatures

This idea is in line with PO2/TransformON, which already model transformation processes for food, feed, and bioproducts.

Different ontologies cover other parts of this picture:

- **FoodOn**: provides a rich vocabulary for food ingredients and products (*e.g.*, eggs, pasta, vegetables, lasagne), so we can “tag” recipe components consistently
- **PO2/TransformON**: focusses on processes and steps—such as boiling, frying, fermenting—and the inputs/outputs of these transformations
- **OBI (Ontology for Biomedical Investigations)**: offers a general model for experimental protocols; its structure can inspire how we organise recipes as protocols
- **PATO (Phenotypic Quality Ontology)**: can be used to label qualities of dishes such as “creamy texture” or “golden colour”

In computational terms, recipes can be represented as knowledge graphs (for example, using RDF/OWL). In such graphs, **nodes** represent ingredients, tools, steps, and dishes, and **edges** represent relations like “is input of,” “results in,” or “has quality.”

Prototype recipe ontologies already support:

- Semantic search: *e.g.*, “find all recipes that involve boiling and pasta”
- Automatic adaptation: *e.g.*, substitute equivalent ingredients
- AI-driven cooking systems: *e.g.*, generate or adapt recipes to dietary constraints

However, some challenges remain:

- How to distinguish acceptable variations from new recipes
- How much detail to include (broad description vs. precise times and temperatures)
- How to connect cultural and aesthetic aspects (from philosophical analysis) with the formal structures needed for computation

5.2 Ontological questions and modelling implications

This section looks at recipes using several **top-level ontologies**—very general frameworks used in applied ontology, such as BFO, DOLCE, and UFO. It also connects them with OBO ontologies like FoodOn and PO2/TransformON. The goal is to show how these choices affect the design of the RELISH data architecture.

In BFO, recipes can be described as a kind of information content entity—that is, a piece of information (like a plan or instruction set) that depends on physical carriers (books, files, memories) but is not identical to any one of them. A printed page or a webpage is a copy of the recipe, not the recipe itself.

In this framework:

- The recipe is an information artefact with directive force: it tells us what to do
- Cooking processes are the events in which the recipe is carried out (mixing, baking, *etc.*)
- Dishes (meals) are the material results of those processes

This gives us a clear three-level picture:

1. **Recipe as plan:** a directive piece of information
2. **Cooking as process:** the execution of that plan in space and time
3. **Dish as product:** the physical result that remains after cooking

This is close to what some “plan ontologies” (such as PlanOnt) already do: they distinguish between a plan, the event of executing it, and the resulting product.

This three-level model has two main consequences:

- It places recipes in the broader family of cultural artefacts: their importance is not just what they describe, but how they guide actions (Borghini 2015; Borghini and Engisch 2022)
- It highlights a layered structure in cooking practices:
 - An informational layer (plans)
 - A procedural layer (processes)
 - A material layer (outputs)

This structure helps us analyse questions about identity and authenticity of dishes (Sciacca 2020), the variability of executions (Fox 2020), and the transmission of culinary knowledge (Borghini 2015).

Different foundational ontologies would describe recipes in slightly different ways. See **Table 1** for a simplified form.

Table 1: Foundational ontologies' approach to describing recipes (*simplified*).

ONTOLOGY	HOW IT CLASSIFIES "RECIPE"	RELATION TO DISH	MAIN IDEA ABOUT IDENTITY	NORMS
BFO	An <i>information content entity</i> (type of informational object)	A dish <i>realises</i> the recipe when the plan is executed	Identity tied to structure of ingredients + steps	YES: plans are prescriptive
DOLCE	A <i>description/plan</i> (abstract social object)	The cooking event <i>realises</i> the plan	Identity tied to the description and its function	Strong emphasis on norms
UFO	A <i>social / normative description</i>	Dishes are <i>situations</i> that result from following the plan	Identity tied to intentions + description	Explicitly normative (recipes as rules)

5.2.1 Recipes as social objects

Recipes are **social objects**. Their existence depends on being recognised, used, and passed on within a culture.

They are:

- Information artefacts: structured sets of instructions (ingredients, quantities, steps)
- Normative: they tell people what should be done, not just what was done
- Type-like: one and the same recipe can have many copies and versions

A single recipe can appear in many forms: a page in a printed cookbook; a handwritten note, a blog post or PDF, or even as memorised instructions passed on orally within a family.

These are all expressions or bearers of the same underlying **recipe-type**. They are not the recipe itself, but they encode it with different degrees of precision. Identical material or digital copies of a recipe may preserve the same representation across time and place. By contrast, oral, fragmentary, simplified, or damaged versions may be “lossy” representations: they preserve only part of the information required to reconstruct the recipe. In such cases, the persistence of a recipe also depends on the availability of a competent interpretive context, or “recipe parser,” able to recover missing or implicit information.

By tracking how one expression comes from another (e.g., from grandma’s oral recipe to a handwritten notebook, then to an online post), we can:

- Reconstruct the lineage of a recipe
- Understand how it has been transmitted and adapted
- Identify families of related recipes (Sciacca 2020)

This gives a layered picture:

- *Recipe-types*: Abstract social/informational entities
- *Recipe-expressions*: Concrete bearers (documents, files, memories)
- *Provenance links*: Relations that record who copied or adapted what, and when

This helps us see culinary knowledge as cultural and informational: recipes are stable enough to support traditions while flexible enough to allow variation and innovation.

5.2.2 *Recipes as plans or norms*

A central question includes: Should we treat recipes as descriptions of what people did in the past, or as plans/norms that guide what people should do in the future?

Recent work suggests the second option: recipes are best understood as plans or norms (Borghini and Engisch 2022; Fox 2020). They are designed to guide action towards a goal (the finished dish).

To model recipes as plans, we can use a **plan/constraint pattern**:

- **Preconditions**: What must be true before we start (ingredients available, oven preheated, tools ready)
- **Steps**: Ordered actions to perform (whisk, boil, bake)
- **Parameters**: Quantities and values (time, temperature, amounts)
- **Expected Qualities**: What the result should be like (cake risen evenly, sauce thick and creamy)

This structure allows us to talk about **correctness**: we can ask whether a given cooking process respects the constraints of the recipe. It also allows us to **compare** different recipes for the “same” dish by looking at how their constraints differ (Sciacca 2020).

With **provenance tools**, we can also track what happens when people break the rules: sometimes constraint violations fail, yet sometimes they lead to innovations that later become new standards for a recipe.

Representing recipes as plans 1) emphasises their normative side (they set standards), 2) allows us to reason about variation and innovation, and 3) puts recipes in the same family as algorithms, workflows, or engineering specifications.

5.2.3 *The identity of recipes in ontology*

A major debate concerns what makes a recipe “the same” recipe.

In BFO and DOLCE, identity is usually tied to the **informational structure**: the organised representation of ingredients, steps, and parameters. According to these ontologies, so long as that structure remains the same, the recipe remains the same, regardless of which book or website carries it.

In UFO, more weight is placed on **intentions** and **norms**. A recipe’s identity depends not only on its structure and also on the intentions of its creator(s), and the accepted standards for correct execution in a given culinary community.

In this view, a recipe remains “the same” so long as people in that community recognise it as such and treat it as prescribing a particular dish.

5.2.4 *A standard pattern from applied ontology*

Applied ontology often uses a **realisation pattern** to connect plans, processes, and outputs. Applied to cooking:

1. *Recipe*: A plan or directive information entity (Borghini and Engisch 2022). It stores the instructions and constraints.
2. *Cooking process*: The concrete event where someone follows the recipe. This can be described using process ontologies such as PO2/ TransformON (Weber et al. 2023).
3. *Dish*: The material product classified by FoodOn (e.g., “lasagna dish,” “bread loaf”), including intermediate products like dough or sauce.

This pattern keeps clear the difference between plan, execution, and product. It also supports reasoning about deviations (where the process does not match the plan). Finally, it allows interoperability: FoodOn for ingredients and dishes, PO2/TransformON for processes.

The result is a coherent framework where recipes, cooking, and dishes can be linked in a unified, machine-readable way.

5.2.5 *Change over time*

Recipes' identities depend on how communities recognise and use them over time.

Following Searle's (1995) account of social objects, a recipe remains “the same recipe” because people keep acknowledging it under the same name and passing it on in a certain way.

Therefore, recipes are **plans** that can be executed in cooking processes, as well as **cultural artefacts** whose existence and continuity depend on social practices (naming, teaching, publishing, protecting).

5.2.6 *The notion of authorship*

Recipes are often linked to specific people or groups, a chef, a family, a restaurant, or a regional community. Further, authorship matters for questions of originality, intellectual property (IP), and authority (“Who has the right to say what the ‘real’ carbonara is?”).

We can encode this with social metadata, such as creator/author, community of reference (*e.g.*, “Roman cuisine”), geographic region, protected status (PDO, PGI, TSG).

We can also model lineages—one recipe may derive from another (*e.g.*, “vegetarian carbonara” from “carbonara”). This lets us build families of recipes and show continuity and innovation (Borghini and Engisch 2022).

Representing recipes in this way complements the earlier layers:

- Informational (what the recipe says)
- Procedural (what one does)
- Social (who created, uses, and recognises it)

5.2.7 *Recipes as normative artefacts*

Recipes are normative artefacts: they say how cooking *should* happen, not just how it *did* happen. This is why we can judge an execution as “correct,” “close enough,” or “wrong.”

We can encode this prescriptive side using languages like OWL (Web Ontology Language), which allow us to write:

- Numeric constraints (*e.g.*, temperature between 180–200°C)
- Qualitative targets (*e.g.*, “creamy texture”, “golden colour”)
- Order and presence of steps (*e.g.*, whisk before folding, all steps required or some optional)

As a normative artefact, a recipe can be seen as a set of validation rules. A cooking process (or a dataset describing it) can be checked against these rules to see how closely it follows a recipe.

5.2.8 Granularity

A practical question is: How much detail do we need?

If the model is too vague, it loses information useful for execution or evaluation. If the model is highly detailed, it may still be abstracted into simpler representations. The concern is therefore not about detail as such, but whether the intended applications require a given level of granularity and whether available tools can support it.

A good solution is a layered model, where different ontologies contribute different levels of detail:

- **FoodOn:** Ingredient and product classes, from very general (“food material”) to very specific (*e.g.*, “Parmigiano Reggiano PDO”). Recipes can then refer either to broad categories or to precise products, depending on the use case.
- **PO2/TransformON:** Process classes and relations (chopping, mixing, fermenting, baking). Actions like “make sauce” can be kept as one step or broken down into smaller steps when needed.

This layered approach keeps interoperability and allows flexibility in the level of detail or granularity.

Figure 4: RELISH Layered Architecture and Data Flow.

5.2.9 Complexity of recipes

Recipes are complex because they **change over time** (adaptation, transmission, codification), **form families of variants** (from informal home versions to legally defined standards), and **involve multiple domains** (gastronomy, nutrition, regulation, cultural heritage).

To model this, we need:

- **Provenance tracking and versioning** to record how one recipe derives from another and how communities regulate identity
- **Alignment among multiple ontologies** for food materials, agricultural concepts, processes, and regulatory systems

A special feature of recipes, compared to technical protocols, is the high level of vagueness and flexibility. Phrases like “season to taste” or “cook until golden brown” assume tacit knowledge and allow acceptable variation (Fox 2020; Borghini and Engisch 2022).

Ontology models ideally should capture this elasticity without compromising reasoning and validation. For example:

- “Add salt to taste” can be modelled as a parameter linked to a qualitative, agent-dependent judgement
- Optional steps (“add cream if desired”) or alternatives (“fry or bake”) can be represented as optional or alternative branches in the plan

Constraint checks then have to tolerate:

- Missing optional steps
- Multiple acceptable paths (*e.g.*, either frying or baking)

5.2.10 Names of Recipes

Names are crucial for how recipes are identified and shared. But naming practices vary widely: one dish may have many names in different languages, or the same word (*e.g.*, “curry”) may cover different dishes in different cultures.

Ontology models must therefore support:

- Multilingual labels
- Regional naming conventions
- Culturally scoped categories

For example, “curry” in South Asian contexts covers a very broad range of dishes, while in many European contexts it often refers to specific spice-based sauces. Ontologies can represent these differences so that, for example, users can query for “Italian regional variants of farinata,” or compare how “curry” is classified in South Asia vs. Europe.

Names also connect to **food safety** and **public health**. Recipes must take into account allergens, contaminants, and critical control points. Linking recipes to food safety ontologies allows systems to highlight risks and necessary precautions.

In the food domain, recipe names often reflect the practical aims, cultural assumptions, and normative commitments of the communities that use them. The same material item or recipe may be classified differently by culinary communities, nutritionists, regulators, historians, local producers, and consumers. Conversely, the same name may refer to partially different objects, dishes, or practices across regions, languages, and traditions.

This is especially relevant for recipe modelling. A recipe name may identify a **family of variants** rather than a single fixed entity. It may refer to a local tradition, a legally protected product, household version, restaurant reinterpretation or broader culinary category. For example, a term such as “curry” may function differently in South Asian, British, or continental European contexts; similarly, names such as “biscuit,” “farinata,” “carbonara,” or “pizza” may carry different classificatory and normative expectations depending on the relevant community.

For RELISH, the implication is that ontology design should not impose a single privileged taxonomy that erases local variation. However, it should not leave naming practices as unstructured and incomparable. The task is to support a simultaneously **pluralist** and **interoperable** model: different community-relative labels and classifications should be allowed to coexist, while their relations are made explicit through mappings, alignments, provenance metadata, and contextual annotations.

This suggests that recipe entities be linked to multilingual labels, as well as to information about the community, region, tradition, institution, or regulatory framework in which a given label is used. In so doing, the recipe visualisation tool can support culturally sensitive search and comparison. Users should be able to ask, for example, how a recipe is named in different regions, which variants are grouped under the same label, which communities recognise a given version as authentic, or how legal, culinary and local classifications diverge.

Such a model treats diversity in naming as a resource rather than as a problem to be eliminated. Ontological interoperability is achieved by avoiding homogenising food vocabularies and instead making explicit the relations between partially overlapping vocabularies.

5.2.11 Gastrospace and situated food practices

Recipes are also embedded in spaces of production, preparation, distribution, and consumption. Food is grown, processed, cooked, served, sold, and eaten in specific places, and these places contribute to shaping the meaning, function, and identity of food practices.

As such, ontologies should ideally avoid treating spatial entities and relations as a neutral background. The concept of **gastrospace** is useful in this respect (Bonotti et al. 2024). A gastrospace is not simply a physical location such as a kitchen, restaurant, market, dining room or street-food setting. Rather, it is a structured space in which agents, material conditions, practices, and norms interact. A place of eating or cooking may include architectural features, tools, ingredients, rules of access, forms of commensality, expectations about behaviour, and cultural meanings attached to

the food being prepared or consumed. In this sense, food spaces are both material and social.

Integrating a spatial dimension is especially important because the project aims to represent recipes as part of European culinary heritage. A recipe may be linked to a territory, but it also links to routes of migration, trade networks, agricultural landscapes, institutional settings, household practices, festive occasions, and/or commercial environments. The same dish may acquire different meanings depending on whether it is prepared in a family kitchen, served in a restaurant, produced industrially, sold in a market, or presented as part of a heritage event.

A recipe visualisation tool should therefore be able to represent where ingredients come from, where a recipe is consumed, which communities are associated with it, and how spatial contexts affect its interpretation. This can support richer forms of storytelling, allowing users to explore recipes as mobile, situated, and socially meaningful objects.

This approach also converses between ontology and disciplines such as geography, anthropology, sociology, and food history. Ontology does not imply replacing the latter fields' empirical and interpretive work. Rather, it could provide a shared representational framework in which spatial, cultural, and social dimensions are made explicit, compared, and connected across different cases. This could also mean that the semantic model remains open to multiple intended models: the same physical place may be represented differently depending on whether the focus is on production, consumption, access, social interaction, heritage value, sustainability or policy relevance.

Integrating gastrospace into the conceptual framework of RELISH would therefore strengthen the cultural layer of the recipe visualisation tool. It would help prevent recipes from being reduced to abstract sequences of instructions and instead represent them as practices situated in places, communities, infrastructures, and histories.

5.2.12 Food items as material entities and role bearers

A further ontological distinction is important: food items should be modelled as **bearers of context-dependent roles**. The same material entity can be classified in different ways depending on the organism, practice, cultural setting or regulatory framework involved.

For example, a peanut may count as food when eaten as a snack, as an ingredient when used in a sauce, as an allergen when it creates a risk for allergic consumers, as a

contaminant when it appears in a product labelled as peanut-free, or as waste when it is discarded after processing or expiration.

These distinctions are crucial, as the material properties of an item do not exhaust its ontological status within a food system. Some properties can be described independently of context, such as chemical composition, biological origin, or physical structure. Other classifications, however, depend on relational and normative conditions: who consumes the item, how it is used, where it appears, what legal constraints apply, and what cultural meanings are attached to it.

In other words, “being food”, “being an ingredient”, “being an allergen,” or “being waste” cannot be assumed as fixed intrinsic categories. Entities acquire roles in specific contexts. This has direct modelling consequences: ingredients should not be represented only as stable entries in a list, and should also be linked to the roles they play within recipes, practices, places, and user contexts. The same entity may need to be visualised differently depending on whether the tool is tracing culinary tradition, allergen risk, ingredient mobility, sustainability, waste, or historical transformation.

This role-based modelling approach allows RELISH to connect material description with cultural interpretation and technical interoperability.

5.3 FoodOn

FoodOn is a major ontology for food developed from 2016 to 2018 by Damion Dooley and collaborators (including Griffiths, Buttigieg, Hoehndorf, Lange, and others). Its goal is to offer a “farm-to-fork” vocabulary that unifies existing food classification systems (such as LanguaL and FoodEx2) and fits the OBO Foundry standards (Dooley, Andrés-Hernández, et al. 2024).⁶

Today, FoodOn contains more than 16,000 classes covering:

- Food ingredients (fruits, vegetables, meat, fish, cereals)
- Processed products (bread, cheese, drinks)
- Processes and treatments (cooking, fermentation, freezing)
- Nutritional properties and allergens
- Contaminants

⁶“FoodOn: a harmonised food ontology to increase global food traceability, quality control and data integration” (Dooley et al. 2018) presents FoodOn’s core design.

It is aligned with **NCBITAXON**⁷ for biological taxonomy, **ChEBI**⁸ for chemical entities, and **ENVO** for environments.

FoodON is available in OWL, RDF, and OBO formats, and hosted via OBO Foundry, GitHub, and AgroPortal.

Its main achievements include:

- **Semantic interoperability:** FoodOn can connect food, nutrition, and environmental datasets and enable FAIR⁹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data integration.
- **Mapping to standards:** FoodOn is already aligned with several food and biomedical resources, including LanguaL and selected nutritional databases. Further alignment with FoodEx2 (the European Food Safety Authority [EFSA] classification), and AGROVOC (the FAO thesaurus) should be treated as ongoing or future work rather than already completed.

FoodOn has practical applications in food traceability and supply chain quality, nutrition and health (*e.g.*, allergens, diets), microbiology and genomics (linking foods and microbes), and circular bioeconomy projects (via integration with PO2/TransformON).

Overall, this ontology provides the semantic backbone for prototype digital tools that support search, annotation, and analysis of food data.

To cover the full lifecycle of recipes and their realisations, FoodOn can be complemented by further alignments and mappings, especially with:

- **Processing modelling resources:** FoodOn already includes a hierarchy of food transformation processes, including cooking, fermentation, freezing, and related treatments. PO2/TransformON can complement FoodOn by offering a process-oriented model for food, feed, bioproducts, and biowaste transformation, especially where input-output relations, process parameters, and links to FoodEx2-oriented content are relevant.
- **AGROVOC:** the FAO multilingual thesaurus for agriculture and food, that integrates FoodOn classes with broader agricultural, botanical, and trade concepts.

⁷ National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) for organismal classification and taxonomy

⁸ Chemical Entities of Biological Interest

⁹ FAIR principles can be useful but are not necessarily clear or understood the same way by different communities. They are interpreted in practice and out of specific contexts.

- **FoodEx2:** EFSA's classification system for exposure assessment and regulation, ensuring compatibility with regulatory use cases.

FoodOn also includes classes for kinds of hazardous foods, including allergens, as well as contaminants such as heavy metals and microbes. Recipes can refer to these classes so that users can query recipes containing specific allergens, or identify steps where contamination risks (*e.g.*, those associated with raw chicken) must be controlled.

Once relevant database links are developed, visual tools built on them could show:

- Where allergens or contaminants may enter a recipe
- Which steps are safety-critical
- Which processes are relevant for reducing or controlling hazards

This would require connecting kinds of food to the processes required to make them safe, edible, or culturally appropriate.

5.4 Related areas of formalisation

Several related lines of work of note include:

- Michaela Kümpel (AICOR Institute for Artificial Intelligence, University of Bremen) has contributed to ontology integration and was part of the organising committee of IFOW, promoting efforts to formalise food concepts and processes (see for example Kümpel and Beetz 2023)
- Bart Gajderowicz (School of Computing, Utah State University) has developed ontologies for accountability, traceability, and impact management in agri-food systems (see Gajderowicz et al. 2025).
- Magalie Weber (INRAE French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment) and colleagues created an ontology for structuring knowledge about consumer food behaviour (presented at IFOW 2025; see Weber et al. 2025).
- There is emerging work on behaviour change, such as the COMFOCUS ontology for food consumer science, studying how formal models can support more sustainable eating habits.
- Susan Michie (Centre for Behaviour Change, University College London) and colleagues developed the Theory and Techniques of Behaviour Change

framework (see Michie and Johnston 2012). This framework shows how behaviour-change interventions can be formalised and queried, offering a useful model for representing consumer behaviour and sustainable food practices.

- Janna Hastings (Idiap Research Institute; University of Zurich) and colleagues contribute methods from biomedical ontologies, offering tools and inspiration for structuring food and consumer behaviour ontologies (see Schenk et al. 2025).

Overall, the formal ontology of recipes benefits from computational modelling to approach cultural heritage and integrate normative philosophy.

In the last five years, we have seen stronger links between food ontologies (FoodOn, TransformON, COMFOCUS) and broader integration efforts (such as IFOW). But important challenges remain:

- Existing food ontologies and integrations can be too vague or not fit-for-purpose
- Misalignment between technical interoperability and cultural diversity
- Limitations of many systems in representing normative and evaluative dimensions.

Future work must keep exploring how recipes—as information artefacts, processes, and social objects—can be modelled in ways that help both technical systems and cultural communities.

A minimal digital architecture building on these insights could look like:

1. **Data layer:** A collection of recipes, ingredients, processes, and sources (*e.g.*, in CSV files or Google Sheets)
2. **Semantic layer:** Mappings to FoodOn (products, ingredients, allergens) and PO2/TransformON (process steps, inputs, outputs)
3. **Backend:** A service that cleans and exposes the data via APIs (*e.g.*, JSON-LD/RDF)
4. **Frontend:** A user-friendly interface with semantic search, filters (ingredients, allergens, geographic origin), and explanations in natural language.
5. **Compliance layer:** FAIR exports and explicit links to ontology concepts to ensure traceability and reuse.

Such a tool would improve interoperability and reuse of recipe data across research, education, and policy, as well as strengthen traceability of recipes and processes. Likewise, this architecture would make it easier to integrate ethical and normative insights from the philosophy of food into practical, digital applications.

Recipe ontological analysis thus requires tools capable of capturing both informational and processual aspects. Similar to experimental protocols in the life sciences, recipes can be represented as structured workflows with inputs (ingredients, tools, energy), transformation processes (cutting, boiling, fermenting), and outputs (intermediate or final dishes). These representations enable computational uses, such as semantic search, recipe adaptation, and integration with AI-driven systems.

In line with this perspective, initiatives such as FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW) have advanced the discussion on how to formalise recipes as culturally embedded yet computationally tractable objects (Dooley et al. 2018; Dooley, Weber, et al. 2024; Weber et al. 2023).

5.5 How recipes can be formalised

From a formal ontology perspective, recipes can be modelled as **workflows**: first, we have the *inputs*, such as ingredients, water, energy, tools; then the *process steps*, such as cutting, boiling, frying, fermenting, mixing; finally, the *outputs*, such as intermediate dishes and the final dish. There are also some constraints, like the required techniques, time intervals, and temperatures. This workflow model aligns with PO2/TransformON, which models transformation processes in food, feed, and bioproducts.

Recipes as ontologically structured workflows are similar to experimental protocols in the life sciences. However, there are few ontologies so far that can capture each of workflow aspect for recipes: FoodOn provides the taxonomy for food ingredients and categories, allowing annotation of recipe components (*e.g.*, eggs, pasta, vegetables); PO2/TransformON captures procedural aspects, such as boiling, frying, or fermenting; OBI offers a good model for structuring protocols, which can inspire recipe representation; PATO can be used to annotate qualitative outcomes of dishes (*e.g.*, creamy texture, golden colour).

In computational ontology, recipes can be represented as **knowledge graphs** (RDF/OWL), where nodes represent ingredients and processes, and edges encode relations such as “is input of” or “results in.” Prototype recipe ontologies enable semantic search (*e.g.*, all recipes involving boiling and pasta), automatic adaptation

(substitution of equivalent ingredients) and support for AI-based culinary systems (generating or adapting recipes to dietary requirements).

There are still some open challenges, such as distinguishing acceptable variations from fundamentally new recipes; deciding the appropriate level of detail (high-level description vs. precise parameters such as cooking times); and interoperability, which refers to integrating cultural and aesthetic dimensions (philosophical analysis) with computational structures (formal ontologies).

6 Discussion

This section discusses what we have learned from our review of existing food-related ontologies and why these results matter for the RELISH project. Our review confirms that there is already a rich ecosystem of ontologies for food, processes, and consumer behaviour, together with a substantial philosophical and methodological literature on recipes as cultural and normative objects.

Taken together, these resources provide complementary building blocks that RELISH can reuse and combine, rather than reinventing the wheel. At the same time, several critical challenges remain, especially in areas that are central for RELISH: historical recipe corpora, the operational connection between data and ontologies, and the representation of cultural heritage, temporality, and narrative aspects in machine-readable form.

6.1 Comparing existing food ontologies

There are mature, shared vocabularies for food products and ingredients:

- **FoodOn** gives detailed classes for raw ingredients, processed products, prepared dishes, allergens, contaminants, and some processing steps. It is already linked to major international standards and classifications (e.g., food safety and agricultural thesauri). If RELISH uses FoodOn terms, its data can be more easily connected to external datasets and regulatory frameworks.

A second group of ontologies focuses on processes and transformations:

- **PO2/TransformON** provides a way to describe cooking and processing steps (such as chopping, boiling, frying, fermenting) and how they are ordered in time.

- Work on protocol ontologies (such as OBI) shows how complex procedures can be broken down into inputs, steps, and outputs. This can inspire how we represent recipes as workflows rather than procedural steps.

A third set of resources helps to capture qualities and behaviours:

- **PATO** offers terms for qualities like colour and texture, which are useful for describing the desired outcome of a dish (e.g., “golden crust,” “creamy sauce”).
- **Ontologies for consumer food behaviour** such as COMFOCUS show how to describe choices, habits, and contexts of eating. These are relevant for RELISH when it wants to link recipes to questions of sustainability, health, or everyday cooking practices.

Finally, initiatives like the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW) demonstrate that there is an active community working on ontology integration for food, and that FoodOn, TransformON and related ontologies are already being aligned with each other.

6.2 Reuse and applicability

For RELISH, ontologies are practical tools for structuring, connecting, and interpreting recipe data. They can support the recipe visualisation platform in several ways:

- They allow us to describe recipes in a standard way, using agreed terms for ingredients, processes, and qualities. This is essential if different partners and datasets in RELISH are to “speak the same language.”
- They make it possible to ask meaningful questions regarding recipes, such as “show recipes from this region without nut allergens,” “find recipes that use fermentation,” or “compare variants of the same dish in different countries.”
- They help to connect recipes to wider concerns, such as food safety (through allergens and contaminants), nutrition, and sustainable practices, because they are already linked to regulatory and scientific vocabularies.

In this sense, the main finding is that RELISH can reuse FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, PATO, and consumer-behaviour ontologies as core components of its own data model, instead of inventing a completely new system.

6.3 Recommendations for RELISH visualisation tool

This review and findings suggest a clear direction for the design of the RELISH infrastructure:

- RELISH should adopt FoodOn as a central reference for ingredients and food products and align it with PO2/TransformON for process steps.
- It should reuse existing models for protocols, qualities, and consumer behaviour where possible, to stay compatible with ongoing work in food science and public health.
- On top of this, RELISH should add a cultural and narrative layer: concepts for recipe identity, authenticity, local variants, historical evolution, and normative rules.

In summary, the technical foundation for representing food and processes already exists, but **the cultural and heritage-oriented extensions are still missing**. RELISH is well positioned to fill this gap by integrating and enriching existing food ontologies to support a recipe visualisation tool that serves both technical interoperability and the storytelling ambitions of the project.

6.4 Gaps, unresolved questions, research opportunities

Despite the strengths of existing ontologies and conceptual work, several questions remain unresolved. They concern both content (what is represented) and infrastructure (how it is represented and used).

This subsection outlines the most relevant gaps and challenges that emerge from Sections 3 and 4 of this report and that motivate future opportunities for research development within RELISH.

6.4.1 *Historical recipe corpora and coverage*

Current food ontologies have been largely developed in connection with **contemporary** food systems, public health and regulatory needs. By contrast, RELISH places strong emphasis on historical recipe corpora and on recipes as elements of European (and neighbouring) cultural heritage.

RELISH and its partners are actively exploring a variety of historical sources: digitised early modern and modern European recipe collections; archives of Arabic recipes, Catalan, and other Iberian materials; collections from the Canary Islands and broader

Mediterranean contexts; as well as local and regional cookbooks that have not yet been systematically analysed.

Many of these corpora are:

- Heterogeneous in format (manuscripts, printed books, digital transcriptions)
- Multilingual (*e.g.*, Arabic, Italian, Spanish, Catalan, French, English)
- Only partially transcribed, cleaned, or structured
- Loosely indexed, often with minimal metadata

At present, there is no consolidated methodology for connecting such historical corpora to ontologies like FoodOn or PO2/TransformON in a scalable, reproducible way. This raises several queries and opportunities:

- How can we systematically identify and prioritise recipe corpora that are most relevant for modelling European food heritage, while acknowledging transnational influences (*e.g.*, Arabic traditions in Mediterranean cuisines)?
- What degree of cleaning, normalisation, and segmentation are required before these corpora can be meaningfully annotated with ontology terms?
- How can we simultaneously preserve the historical specificity of sources (*e.g.*, obsolete ingredients, now-unusual techniques, archaic measurements) and map them onto modern vocabularies?

Addressing these questions provides opportunities for collaboration between digital humanities, food history, and ontology engineering that extend beyond the scope of this deliverable but could generate research and practical impact.

6.4.2 Operational integration of data and ontologies

A second set of gaps concerns the operational integration between recipe data and ontologies. Our conceptual analysis shows why recipes can be modelled as normative plans, workflows and cultural artefacts; existing ontologies provide the basic classes and relations.

However, there is still **no end-to-end pipeline** that takes historical or contemporary recipes and recipe data and reliably turns them into semantically enriched, ontology-based representations.

Open questions include:

- How can we design practical workflows that start from raw texts (*e.g.*, a digitised manuscript collection of recipes) and produce structured data aligned with FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and related ontologies?
- Which combination of manual expert curation, rule-based methods and machine-learning/LLM-based tools is most appropriate for tasks, such as ingredient recognition, process extraction, temporal annotation, and identifying cultural metadata (origin, tradition, authorship)?
- How should we represent uncertainty and disagreement in data (*e.g.*, competing interpretations of a historical ingredient, ambiguous instructions, contested attributions of authorship)?
- What metadata standards and provenance models are needed to record who annotated what, with which tools, and at which level of confidence?

Therefore, one major challenge for future work is to design and test shared annotation and integration workflows that can be reused by different partners and extended to new corpora.

As highlighted by Hackathon Firenze and other events, temporal and processual aspects of recipes are crucial for understanding both identity and heritage:

- The distinction between constitutive and non-constitutive phases (*e.g.*, leavening vs. optional decoration)
- The role of efficiency (accelerated or extended processes, such as chemically aged rum or shelf-life extension techniques)
- Embedding recipes in contexts such as seasonality, ritual calendars, and the transition from niche to global foods

Existing ontologies offer partial solutions (for example, process hierarchies in TransformON, temporal regions in some upper ontologies), but they do not yet provide a fully satisfactory way to:

- Represent temporal constraints that are identity-defining (*e.g.*, minimum leavening time for a specific bread)
- Link recipes to cultural calendars (“recipes for Ramadan,” “Carnival sweets,” dishes associated with specific festivals or life events)
- Model evolving contexts, such as the transformation of a local dish into a global product or shifts in perceived authenticity over time

These issues remain open and call for further collaboration between ontologists, philosophers of food, and food historians.

6.4.3 Evaluation, user studies, and quantitative indicators

The state of the art in food ontologies is relatively rich from a technical standpoint but still limited in terms of systematic evaluation with end users, especially when recipes are framed as cultural heritage objects.

Some open questions include:

- How can we define evaluation metrics that are meaningful for both technical partners and cultural stakeholders (*e.g.*, curators, food historians, chefs, educators)?
- What kinds of user studies are needed to assess whether ontology-based visualisations help users understand recipe lineages, ingredient mobilities, or authenticity claims?
- How might we combine qualitative feedback (interviews, workshops, focus groups) with quantitative indicators (usage statistics, task-completion rates, accuracy of semantic search) to evaluate the success of the RELISH tools?

These questions are only partially addressed in existing literature and require dedicated methodological work, drawing on social sciences and HCI.

6.5 Summary of recommendations and implications

Taken together, the findings from food ontologies and the identified gaps suggest a clear direction for the design of the RELISH infrastructure.

RELISH should:

- **Adopt FoodOn as a central reference** for ingredients and food products and align it with PO2/TransformON for process steps.
- **Reuse existing models for protocols, qualities, and consumer behaviour** wherever possible, in order to remain compatible with ongoing work in food science, nutrition and public health.
- **Build on the conceptual analysis of recipes as normative, cultural and informational objects** to design a semantic layer that can support identity, variation, authenticity and heritage dimensions.

- **Add a cultural and narrative layer** on top of existing ontologies, including concepts for recipe identity, authenticity, local variants, historical evolution, typicality, seasonality, and links to historical corpora.

The open questions identified below highlight current limitations of the state of the art and suggest at least four interrelated strands of future work:

- **Building and curating historical recipe corpora:** Systematic identification, digitisation, transcription, and cleaning of key historical recipe collections (including Arabic, Catalan, Canary and wider European corpora), to create open, accessible, well-documented datasets that can serve as testbeds for ontology-based modelling
- **Designing annotation and integration pipelines:** Development and evaluation of semi-automated pipelines that connect raw textual data to FoodOn, PO2/TransformON and related ontologies, combining NLP/LLM-based tools with expert curation and explicit uncertainty management
- **Extending ontologies for temporality, context, and heritage:** Formalisation of temporal phases, cultural calendars, typicality, and authenticity within or alongside existing ontologies, in close dialogue with philosophers of food, historians, and heritage institutions
- **User-centred evaluation and governance models:** Co-design of evaluation frameworks, and governance procedures with stakeholders (chefs, curators, educators, communities), ensuring that recipe ontologies remain both technically robust and culturally legitimate

These recommendations and implications can deepen and extend the conceptual and ontological framework developed in RELISH, transform scattered historical and contemporary recipe collections into shared, semantically enriched resources, and deliver tools and infrastructures that are usable not only within RELISH, but also by a wider ecosystem of researchers, cultural institutions, policymakers, and the public.

7 Significance and Potential Impact

An important implication of D4.3 is that RELISH does not operate in isolation. The project is already positioned within a broader interdisciplinary landscape that includes food ontology initiatives, philosophy of food, digital heritage research, consumer behaviour modelling, and semantic web communities. This broader

landscape provides opportunities and potential spaces for collaboration, feedback, and future impact.

First, several of the groups, workshops, and initiatives discussed in this report can provide valuable input for RELISH. Communities working on FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, IFOW, and related ontology projects offer conceptual resources, technical standards, and modelling experience that can help RELISH refine its semantic infrastructure and improve interoperability. Their work can support RELISH in aligning its own models with established vocabularies and in identifying which aspects of recipe representation can be directly reused and which require extension.

Second, RELISH can contribute something distinctive to these extant projects and communities. Existing food ontologies are especially strong in areas such as ingredients, products, food transformation, traceability, and consumer behaviour, but they are less developed when it comes to recipes as historical, cultural, and narrative objects. RELISH can therefore function as a test case for showing how ontology-based approaches may be extended toward questions of cultural heritage, recipe identity, authenticity, temporality, storytelling, and cross-cultural mobility. In this sense, the project may provide both content and conceptual opportunities that broaden the scope of current food ontology work.

Third, there is clear collaborative potentials with academic and institutional groups beyond formal ontology in the narrow sense. Food historians, philosophers of food, digital humanities scholars, museum and archive professionals, and public-facing heritage institutions may all benefit from a framework that makes recipes more searchable, comparable, and visually intelligible across time and place. The RELISH approach may also be relevant for stakeholders concerned with education, sustainability, and food culture communication, because ours prioritises narrative accessibility.

In sum, RELISH can further exploit: **Technical significance**, because it contributes to semantic modelling and interoperability; **Conceptual significance**, because it clarifies the status of recipes as cultural and normative objects; and, **Collaborative significance**, because it opens a space of exchange between ontology engineering, philosophy, food studies, and cultural heritage practice. This broader impact is worth emphasising, since RELISH connects communities that do not usually work together in a sustained manner.

8 Future Directions for Automation with LLMs

As recipe ontologies expand to cover ingredients, processes, safety constraints, and cultural classifications, their long-term utility depends on community-driven governance and robust validation mechanisms.

Ontologies in this domain are dynamic artefacts: they must incorporate new recipes, terminological variants, and safety regulations, while avoiding uncontrolled drift or semantic inconsistency.

To achieve this, governance structures should **combine human-in-the-loop curation with semi-automated assistance** from large language models (LLMs). LLMs can suggest candidate classes, relations, or alignments (*e.g.*, proposing a mapping between a new ingredient and an existing FoodOn class) with mediation by expert curators. A workflow should therefore involve:

- Automated suggestions from LLMs trained on culinary and food safety corpora
- Curator review boards comprising domain experts, ontology engineers, and cultural stakeholders
- Consensus mechanisms (*e.g.*, voting, commentary periods) to ratify additions or revisions

This workflow ensures that updates benefit from scalable automation without compromising on cultural and scientific accuracy. Each ontology change should be evaluated against a set of **competency questions**—formal queries that the ontology is expected to answer (Grüniger and Fox 1995). For example:

- Which recipes contain nut allergens?
- What regional variants of *farinata* exist in Tuscany and Liguria?
- Which process steps eliminate Salmonella contamination risk?

Proposed changes are validated if they maintain or improve the ontology's ability to answer such questions, ensuring continuity of reasoning capabilities. Ontologies must preserve transparent provenance of changes. Each release should be assigned a version IRI, with change logs documenting modifications, deprecations, and alignments. This allows downstream applications to trace ontology evolution and to maintain reproducibility in scholarly and regulatory contexts. Version control systems (*e.g.*, Git-based repositories) provide technical infrastructure to track community contributions and ensure rollback capability when errors are introduced.

LLMs can also support automatic extraction of ontology elements from textual corpora such as scientific papers, recipes, and regulatory documents. Some potential tasks may include identifying candidate classes and concepts; extracting semantic relations (*e.g.*, “ingredient-of,” “produced-by,” “is-step-of”); suggesting taxonomic hierarchies.

Such systems would reduce manual ontology engineering, leaving domain experts with the validation and refinement of AI-generated suggestions. Future pipelines will likely combine LLM-based extraction with human-in-the-loop verification. They may help with ontology alignment and mapping, for example aligning FoodOn with PO2/TransformON, AGROVOC, FoodEx2, and other ontologies currently resource-intensive. LLMs can facilitate this by generating candidate equivalences, synonym mappings, and subclass relations.

Hybrid approaches combining semantic embeddings with logical axioms promise to automate ontology integration at scale. Ontology-based questions and answering LLMs can function as natural language interfaces to ontologies. For example, a user query “show me all recipes with legumes and boiling process” could be translated by the LLM into a SPARQL or OWL query.

With appropriate governance, LLM automation could democratise access to ontology-driven data and represent formal knowledge in a user-friendly, interactive format.

Ontologies evolve continuously as new recipes, diets, and industrial processes emerge. LLMs can monitor literature, datasets, and online resources to propose ontology updates in near real time, creating “living ontologies” that remain up to date without full manual revision. Future AI agents will likely combine LLM capabilities with ontology reasoning. Such agents could generate new recipes, verify their coherence against FoodOn or PO2/TransformON axioms, and provide validated outputs. Ontologies would act as the ground truth ensuring logical consistency and factual reliability.

Furthermore, a critical advantage of LLMs is their ability to generate human-readable explanations. When combined with ontologies, LLMs can justify classifications (*e.g.*, “this recipe is classified as pasta dish because it contains semolina product and boiling as process step”). Philosophy of food can contribute criteria for authenticity, identity, and cultural value, which can enrich automated explanations and align them with normative frameworks.

There are probable challenges to overcome, such that LLMs may propose non-existent or incoherent concepts and logical validation may be required. LLMs can impose sometimes harmful or exclusionary cultural bias and risk of

over-representing Western or globalised categories at the expense of local specificities and complexities. Most significant is the problem of governance—how to ensure that AI-generated updates are vetted and approved by expert communities.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable presents the conceptual and formal modelling of recipes within the RELISH project, drawing on recent philosophical literature and the perspective of top-level ontologies. We identify the central research questions concerning the identity, authorship, and evolution of recipes, and examine how these questions can be operationalised in ontology-based data architectures.

The report further situates recipes in relation to social practices, authenticity, and normative constraints, discussing their implications for digital representation and visualisation tools. Competency questions are provided to connect the theoretical framework with practical implementation, ensuring that the RELISH infrastructure is aligned with state-of-the-art scholarship and capable of supporting interoperable, culturally sensitive, and semantically robust representations of recipes.

In summary, D4.3:

- Provides a systematic literature review in the philosophy of food, complemented by references to workshops and thematic events
- Identifies key ontologies (FoodOn, PO2/TransformON) and preliminary analysis of their compatibility with other OBO/FAIR standards
- Defines the minimum requirements for a prototype digital tool, including: (a) semantic search on food concepts, (b) guided annotation of recipes and processes, (c) export of interoperable datasets (RDF/CSV)
- Clarifies the conceptual and practical relevance of the philosophy of food for food data modelling
- Maps and harmonises relevant ontologies (FoodOn, PO2/TransformON, and others) in relation to concrete use cases
- Establishes the semantic and functional foundation for a prototype digital tool enabling food data search, annotation, and analysis, with outputs interpretable by non-experts

Ultimately, D4.3 is an intellectual and technical resource for the recipe visualisation tool. Its role as a protocol is targeted to RELISH technical partners. However, D4.3 benefits the broader RELISH project in that it maintains the coherence of frameworks and core objectives working with recipes—from data to applications. D4.3 supports RELISH’s overarching goals: to use recipes as vehicles of cultural heritage, sustainability, and social innovation for Europe’s future.

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Additional Resources

Web:

FoodOn: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41538-018-0032-6>

Food process ontology requirements (SWJ): <https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/content/food-process-ontology-requirements>

OBO Foundry Food Ontology Interconnectivity: <https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/system/files/swj2971.pdf>

PO2/TransformON: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41538-023-00221-2>

IFOW 2021: <https://foodon.org/ifow-2021-workshop/>

Bots in the Kitchen (Webinar):

https://www.mcgill.ca/desautels/files/desautels/230826_mcgill_fci_webinar_sept_26_11-1_et_a.borghini_bot_in_the_kitchen_digital_food_transformation.pdf

Bart Gajderowicz – Publications and Events: <https://bartg.org/publications>

Publications:

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